

A NEW METHOD FOR MEASUREMENT OF CARBON FIBER AXIAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND SOME APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

A new method to estimate the axial compressive strength of carbon fibers from the fiber fragment lengths produced by subjecting them to a strain greater than the fiber ultimate strain was previously proposed. The estimated compressive strength of carbon fiber is approximately 25 ~ 60% of tensile strength for PAN-based fibers, while it is approximately 10 ~ 35% for Pitch-based fibers. An obvious correlation between the fiber axial compressive strength and compressive strength of unidirectional composites is found.

INTRODUCTION

Relationship between the mechanical properties (strength, fracture strain and modulus) of composites in tension and those of the fibers used as reinforcement have been studied both experimentally and theoretically in fairly great detail. However, there is practically no study on the mechanical properties of composites in compression in spite of their possible dependences on the compressive characteristics of reinforcing fibers. It is difficult to determine accurately the axial compressive properties of reinforcing fibers. We previously proposed a new method to estimate the axial compressive strength of carbon fibers from the fiber fragment lengths. Namely, if a sufficiently long fiber is embedded in the resin matrix and the system is compressed, the fiber eventually breaks into many pieces, on the assumption that a theory according to Kelly et al.^{1,2}, while assuming that the yield shear strength at the fiber-matrix interphase is constant, may be applied to the system in compression. By measuring the lengths of the broken pieces, we estimated the fiber axial compressive strengths. Moreover, we discussed the relationship between the fiber axial compressive strength and compressive strength of unidirectional composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Principle

If a sufficiently long fiber is embedded in the resin matrix and the system is subjected to a tensile strain greater than the fiber ultimate strain, the fiber eventually breaks into many pieces. Assuming that the fiber strength is uniform along the length of the fiber, critical fiber length $(l_c)_{ten}$ in tension is given as³

$$(l_c)_{\text{ten}} = \frac{4}{3} (\bar{l})_{\text{ten}} \quad (1)$$

where $(\bar{l})_{\text{ten}}$ is the mean fragment length. Moreover, according to Kelly et al.^{1,2}, the relationship between critical fiber length $(l_c)_{\text{ten}}$ and the tensile strength of fiber $(\sigma_f)_{\text{ten}}$ results in the following equation :

$$(l_c)_{\text{ten}} = \frac{(\sigma_f)_{\text{ten}} \cdot d}{2 \tau} \quad (2)$$

where τ is the yield shear strength at the fiber-matrix interphase and d is the diameter of the fiber. Accordingly, τ can be determined from Eqs. (1) and (2) by measuring the mean fragment length $(\bar{l})_{\text{ten}}$ in tension.

When the above-mentioned specimen is compressed in the direction of the fiber axis, we assumed that the yield shear strength at the fiber-matrix interphase is the same value as that in tension, but the working direction is the reverse. Therefore, if the specimen is subjected to a compressive strain greater than the fiber ultimate compressive strain, the fiber eventually breaks into many pieces in the same manner as in the case of tension. Measuring the mean fragment length in compression $(\bar{l})_{\text{comp}}$, the critical fiber length in compression $(l_c)_{\text{comp}}$ is given as

$$(l_c)_{\text{comp}} = \frac{4}{3} (\bar{l})_{\text{comp}} \quad (3)$$

Moreover, according to the above-mentioned assumption, the following equation is held:

$$(l_c)_{\text{comp}} = \frac{(\sigma_f)_{\text{comp}} \cdot d}{2 \tau} \quad (4)$$

where $(\sigma_f)_{\text{comp}}$ is the fiber axial compressive strength. As τ and d in Eq. (4) are the same values as those in Eq. (2), if τ is determined by the tensile experiment according to Eq.(2), the fiber axial compressive strength $(\sigma_f)_{\text{comp}}$ can be estimated according to Eq. (4).

In this experiment, to accurately give the fiber the tensile strain, a rectangular beam in which a long fiber was embedded at a constant tension in the neighborhood of the surface was prepared and the four-point bending method was adopted. If the side having a fiber of the specimen is bent outside, the fiber is elongated. If the side having a fiber of the specimen is bent inside, the fiber is compressed.

Preparation of Specimen

The fibers used in this study were PAN-based carbon fibers (Toray, Torayca 7.1 μm in diameter) and Pitch-based carbonfibers (Experimental samples of Toa Nenryo Kogyo, Tonen 10.1 μm in diameter). Moreover, carbonized (higher strength type) and graphitized fibers (higher modulus type) were respectively used. Matrix material was an epoxy resin (Epikote 828, Yuka Shell). Epoxy resin, 100 parts, was mixed with 10 parts of an amine hardening agent (S-Cure 661, Nihon Kayaku). The mixture was agitated thoroughly and then defoamed under vacuum for about 30 min. This mixture was poured into a mold holding a fiber at a constant tension and subjected to curing at 65°C for 17 hr and postcuring at 140°C for 5 hr. The specimen was then allowed to cool to

room temperature at a cooling rate of about 0.5°C/min. The dimension of the mold resulted in a specimen which measured 13(H)x10(W)x210(L). The specimens prepared in this manner were submitted to measurement of fragment length; each specimen was subjected to a tensile (or compressive) strain of 4% at a drop rate of the upper heads of 10 mm/min. Span length was 180 mm. In order to investigate the effect of radially compressing force on the fiber axial compressive strength, measurements were made at intervals of 20°C from 20~140°C. Over 1000 fragments were examined for each experimental condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fiber fragment lengths were measured. Critical fiber length $(l_c)_{ten}$ in tension was then obtained from the mean fragment length $(\bar{l})_{ten}$ according to Eq. (1). Yield shear strength τ at the interphase was obtained from this critical fiber length $(l_c)_{ten}$ according to Eq. (2). Moreover, the relationship between the critical fiber length $(l_c)_{comp}$ in compression, which is obtained from the mean fragment length $(\bar{l})_{comp}$ in compression according to Eq. (3), and the temperature is shown in Fig. 1. The value of fiber axial compressive strength was estimated from the critical fiber length $(l_c)_{comp}$ (Fig. 1) in compression and the yield shear strength τ according to Eq. (4).

Fig. 1 Relation between temperature and critical fiber length in compression. (a) Pitch-based carbon fiber, (b) PAN-based carbon fiber. O:Carbonized fiber,PCT, ●:Graphitized fiber,PGM, Δ: carbonized fiber,T-300, ▲:graphitized fiber,M-40.

When a fiber is embedded in the resin and the system is allowed to cure, the thermal stress $(P)_T$ working perpendicularly on the fiber-resin interface is approximately given by the following equation⁴:

$$(P)_T = \frac{\alpha_m \cdot E_m \cdot \Delta T}{1 + \nu_m} \quad (5)$$

where α is the thermal expansion coefficient, E is the Young's modulus, ν is the Poisson's ratio, ΔT is the difference in temperature from molding temperature and the subscript m denotes matrix. Figure 2 shows the relationship between the estimated compressive strength and the thermal stress. The estimated compressive strength of carbonized and graphitized fibers decreases linearly with decreasing thermal stress.

Fig. 2 Relation between thermal stress and estimated compressive strength.

- : Pitch-based carbonized fiber, PCT,
- : Pitch-based graphitized fiber, PGM,
- △: PAN-based carbonized fiber, T-300,
- ▲: PAN-based graphitized fiber, M-40.

It is conceivable that the real compressive strength of carbonized and graphitized fiber is the strength that the radial compressing force, i.e., the residual thermal stress in this experiment is zero. Accordingly, we considered the value obtained by extrapolating the straight line in Fig. 2 to $(P)_T=0$ as the real compressive strength of carbonized and graphitized fiber and showed those values in Table 1. For comparison, the tensile strength and ratio of compressive strength to the tensile strength are also shown in Table 1. The estimated real compressive strength of PAN-based carbonized fiber (higher strength type) is the highest and Pitch-based carbon fiber follows. For both PAN-based and Pitch-based fibers, the estimated compressive strength of graphitized fiber (higher modulus type) is always less than half of that of carbonized fiber (higher strength type). Furthermore, the ratio of compressive strength to the tensile strength is approximately 35 ~ 60% for carbonized fiber, while its ratio is approximately 10 ~ 25% for graphitized fiber. It is noted that the estimated real

compressive strength of graphitized fiber is remarkably low.

Table 1 Tensile and estimated compressive strength of carbon fiber

Carbon fiber	Pitch-based		PAN-based	
	Carbonized fiber PCT	Graphitized fiber PGM	Carbonized fiber T-300	Graphitized fiber M-40
Tensile strength (σ_f) _{ten} (GPa)	3.34	4.33	3.50	2.88
Estimated compressive strength (σ_f) _{comp} (GPa)	1.25	0.54	2.06	0.78
$\frac{(\sigma_f)_{comp}}{(\sigma_f)_{ten}}$ (%)	37.4	12.5	58.9	27.1

We will discuss now some applications of the method for measuring fiber axial compressive strength. The relationship between the fiber axial compressive strength and compressive strength of unidirectional composites is shown in Fig. 3. Test specimens of composites were cut and tested in accordance with ASTM D 3410-75. Fiber volume fraction V_f was set at 60%. The dotted line shows theoretical values calculated by the following equation:

$$(\sigma_c)_{comp} = (\sigma_f)_{comp} \cdot V_f \quad (6)$$

where $(\sigma_c)_{comp}$ is the compressive strength of composite, $(\sigma_f)_{comp}$ is the fiber compressive strength, V_f is the fiber volume fraction. The experimental values are slightly larger than the theoretical values, but a linear relationship is observed. Therefore, it is found that the experimental values were roughly given by a rule of mixtures.

CONCLUSIONS

If a sufficiently long fiber is embedded in the neighborhood of the surface of rectangular beam and the system is subjected to a tensile (or compressive) strain greater than the fiber ultimate strain according to the bending method, the fiber eventually breaks into many pieces. Measuring the lengths of the broken pieces, attempts were made to estimate the axial compressive strength of the carbon fibers. There is a linear relationship between the estimated compressive strength of carbon fibers and radial compressing force in a temperature range from room temperature to 100 °C. The real compressive strength of the fibers, determined by extrapolating this straight line until the radial compressing force is zero, approximately 25 ~ 60% of tensile strength for PAN-based fibers, while it is approximately 10 ~ 35% for Pitch-based fibers. An obvious correlation between the fiber axial compressive strength and compressive strength of the unidirectional composites is found and the experimental values roughly agreed with the values calculated by a rule of mixtures.

Fig. 3 Relation between estimated compressive strength of carbon fiber and compressive strength of composite. ○:Pitch-based carbonized fiber, PCT, ●:Pitch-based graphitized fiber, PGM, △:PAN-based carbonized fiber, T-300, ▲:PAN-based graphitized fiber, M-40.

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